

Computing Neutron Multiplicity Counting Moments From Forward Monte Carlo Transport Simulations

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ABSTRACT

Modeling and simulation of subcritical systems has a predominant impact on the development, verification, and validation of neutron noise techniques. These techniques are integral to several applications including the identification and characterization of special nuclear material, the development of new detector technology and reactor analysis. Several experimental applications within this space have advanced benchmarking approaches which have traditionally been dominated by integral experiments. Modeling neutron noise measurements requires either computationally expensive analog Monte Carlo simulations or deterministic solutions to adjoint-like transport equations. A methodology is proposed in this work for the computation of adjoint fluxes by tallying a weighted importance from a forward Monte Carlo simulation and it is shown that the importance weight function can be selected to yield moments of the distribution of neutrons interacting with a detector medium. Preliminary results show good agreement with an analytical solution for the first and second moments with decreased accuracy at later measurement times. Although increased noise is observed in the Monte Carlo solution, the maximum absolute error between the analytical and Monte Carlo results are ~ 0.25 and ~ 2.5 for the first and second moments, respectively. Nonetheless, general agreement between the solutions suggests that the approach can be extended to leverage continuous energy cross sections while also utilizing generalized Monte Carlo geometry treatment in production-level codes to calculate quantities of interest to neutron noise analysis techniques.

Keywords: Neutron Multiplicity Moments, Neutron Noise Analysis, Monte Carlo Transport

1. INTRODUCTION

The ability to accurately characterize samples of special nuclear material (SNM) is integral to various applications including reactor noise analysis, nuclear safeguards, and global security and nonproliferation. Feynman-Y analysis is a neutron noise analysis technique that is commonly used in such applications [1, 2]. In this analysis approach, a time-tagged list of data corresponding to detection times within a neutron detector, typically involving ^3He resulting in (n, p) reactions, are binned across various gate widths over a given measurement period [1]. The binned data is then used to construct the probability density function (pdf) of observing a particular quantity of counts within any of the given time bins.

This analysis technique is formulated based on spontaneous fission being a stochastic process that can be described by a Poisson distribution normalized to the mean neutron production rate [2]. A defining characteristic of such processes is that the mean of the distribution is equal to its variance. However, in the presence of induced fission, i.e., a multiplying system, correlated neutrons from fission chains will also be registered introducing a deviation from a Poisson distribution. Thus, the Feynman-Y statistic can be viewed as the “excess variance” as deviating from a Poisson distribution and is defined as

$$Y = \frac{\sigma^2}{\mu} - 1, \quad (1)$$

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where μ and σ^2 are the mean and variance of the neutron count distribution over a specific gate width, respectively. It is noted that Y is computed for a series of gate widths where each has a unique value. The mean and variance of the count distribution are extracted from Feynman histograms generated using the binning technique described and used to compute Y as a function of increasing gate widths. The time evolution of the Feynman- Y function and its asymptotic value provide insight into the system's prompt neutron decay constant (α) and the mean generation time (Λ).

The time-gated moments of the neutron count distribution are also useful for other analysis techniques in addition to Feynman- Y analysis. For instance, the Hage-Cifarelli three parameter model uses moments of the count distribution to infer sample characteristics such as the leakage multiplication (M_L) and the spontaneous fission source strength (F) from which sample mass can be estimated [3]. As such, the quantities of interest to this work are the time-gated moments of the neutron count distribution. Computing these moments has traditionally relied on either computationally expensive Monte Carlo simulations to reproduce list-mode data or deterministic solutions to adjoint-like transport equations. A new approach is demonstrated here where an adjoint solution to the neutron count moment equations is obtained from a forward Monte Carlo simulation thus providing an efficient method to computing these moments.

2. NEUTRON TRANSPORT

The linear time-dependent Boltzmann neutron transport equation is a balance equation describing how neutrons are transported within a system given that there is an external source to the system. The mechanism by which neutrons are born by (α, n) reactions, spontaneous and induced fission reactions is of crucial importance.

2.1. Forward Neutron Transport

Before beginning with the application of adjoint neutron transport flux solutions in obtaining counting statistics for neutrons existing and being lost within a system, it is important to formulate the canonical form of the time-dependent neutron transport equation thus [4]:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t}(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) + \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) + \Sigma_t(\mathbf{x}, E) \psi(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) = \\ = \int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \Sigma_s(\mathbf{x}, E' \rightarrow E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}' \cdot \boldsymbol{\Omega}) \psi(\mathbf{x}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}', t) + \\ + \frac{\chi_p(E)}{4\pi} \int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \bar{v} \Sigma_f(\mathbf{x}, E') \psi(\mathbf{x}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}', t) + \frac{Q(\mathbf{x}, E, t)}{4\pi}. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The production of neutrons via fission processes and the external sources are assumed to be isotropic. The first term on the LHS represent the time-rate of change of the angular flux, ψ . The second term in the LHS is the streaming term of neutrons accounting for neutrons that could "leak" through the system boundary across ∂V , which is sufficiently convex. The third term accounts for any losses due to every collision process. The first term of the RHS accounts for the scattering of neutrons existing in the phase space element, $p' = (\mathbf{x}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}')$ into the phase space element, $p = (\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega})$ at time, t where $p, p' \in P = (V \times 4\pi \times [0, \infty])$. The second term on the RHS accounts for the neutrons existing in p' inducing a fission reaction, introducing \bar{v} prompt fission neutrons into p . The last term is the extraneous source. Equation 2 is subject to the boundary and initial conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) = \psi_b(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t), \quad \mathbf{x} \in \partial V, \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} < 0, E \in [0, \infty], \\ \psi(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, 0) = \psi_i(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}), \quad \mathbf{x} \in V, \boldsymbol{\Omega} \in 4\pi, E \in [0, \infty]. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For ease of notation, Equation 2 can be formulated in simplified operator notation as

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}\psi = \frac{Q}{4\pi'} \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{L} denotes the transport operator on the angular flux, ψ . Encoded within \mathcal{L} are the mechanisms of streaming, scattering and fission as explained above.

2.2. Adjoint Neutron Transport

The adjoint transport equation describes the importance of particular neutrons in phase space, p to some designated “response” function, Q^\dagger . Because of this, the adjoint flux, ψ^\dagger is oftentimes considered the “function of importance”. In order to arrive at the adjoint transport operator as [4] have done, the inner product between two functions, $f(x)$ and $g(x)$, needs to be defined as

$$\langle f(x), g(x) \rangle = \int_{\Delta x} f(x)g(x)dx. \quad (5)$$

If one is to do the same between the “adjoint” flux and the forward flux being acted upon by the forward operators where the inner product is over all phase-space and time, one would conclude succinctly that

$$\left\langle \psi^\dagger, \frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}\psi \right\rangle = \left\langle -\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi^\dagger}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}^\dagger \psi^\dagger, \psi \right\rangle + P_l[\psi, \psi^\dagger], \quad (6)$$

where the non-adjoint operators have a change in sign due to the application of integration-by-parts on the non-symmetric operator, $\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{\Omega} \cdot \nabla$. The $P_l[\psi, \psi^\dagger]$ is the bilinear concomitant that arises from the boundary terms that arise from the very same operation. Assuming that the boundary and temporal conditions are properly defined in order to eliminate the bilinear concomitant, the Lagrange identity is obtained as

$$\left\langle \psi^\dagger, \frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}\psi \right\rangle = \left\langle -\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi^\dagger}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}^\dagger \psi^\dagger, \psi \right\rangle. \quad (7)$$

From Equation 7, one can formulate the adjoint neutron transport equation as

$$-\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \psi^\dagger}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}^\dagger \psi^\dagger = Q^\dagger. \quad (8)$$

Now that the adjoint “adjuncton” transport equation has been formulated, one can move forward with the difference between the inner products of the two equations which is

$$\langle \psi^\dagger, \mathcal{L}\psi \rangle = \langle \mathcal{L}^\dagger \psi^\dagger, \psi \rangle \rightarrow \langle \psi^\dagger, Q \rangle = \langle Q^\dagger, \psi \rangle, \quad (9)$$

where \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{L}^\dagger is the forward and adjoint transport operators encoded with the flux tending terms, respectively.

2.3. Forward-Adjoint Monte Carlo

Firstly, a forward transport equation needs to be formulated with the solution being the Green’s function solution:

$$\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{p}_n, t; t_n)}{\partial t} + \mathcal{L}\mathcal{G}(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{p}_n, t; t_n) = \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_n)\delta(t - t_n). \quad (10)$$

Substituting the Dirac delta function as the forward source in Equation 9, one obtains

$$\left\langle \psi^\dagger, \delta^3(\mathbf{p} - \mathbf{p}_n)\delta(t - t_n) \right\rangle = \left\langle Q^\dagger, \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{p}_n, t; t_n) \right\rangle. \quad (11)$$

The LHS simplifies to $\psi^\dagger(\mathbf{p}_n, t_n)$ by integration over the Dirac delta function, where the equation describing the solution of the adjoint flux normalized by the weight of the particle, w_i , is

$$\psi^\dagger(\mathbf{p}_n, t_n) = \frac{1}{w_i} \int_{\Delta p} d\mathbf{p} \int_{t_i}^{t_f} dt \mathcal{G}(\mathbf{p}; \mathbf{p}_n, t; t_n) Q^\dagger(\mathbf{p}, t). \quad (12)$$

Noting that the track-length normalization is necessary due to every interaction within this particular forward Monte Carlo simulation is treated as a source Dirac delta function (since the simulation is being run as if forward transport is being conducted) and implicit capture is typically utilized for weight adjustment. The power of this particular formulation is quite evident when realizing that all of the track-lengths obtained from a Monte Carlo simulation have already captured all of the physics encoded within the problem (leaving aside statistical convergence). For any set of track-lengths that have been obtained, the adjoint flux can always be computed for various arbitrary response functions or adjoint sources. This implies that any adjoint flux for a certain problem can be computed from only a single Monte Carlo run. The forward-adjoint Monte Carlo method that is used in this work was developed by one of the authors (Colin A. Weaver) and a detailed description of the theory and numerical implementation will be presented in a future publication.

3. NEUTRON COUNTS MOMENT EQUATIONS

The equations appropriate to the time-gated moments of the neutron count distribution have been shown to be adjoint-like transport equations with an inhomogeneous source term [5, 6, 7]. Hence, these equations are readily formulated as adjoint transport equations where the adjoint flux is evaluated by tallying a forward flux with respect to a specific weight function [7, 8]. Much work has been done previously in deriving these equations for the purposes of neutron distribution moment reconstructions for spallation sources, subcritical piles, and noise in reactors. The first adjoint equation in operator notation where the solution is the first moment of the count distribution during a measurement period, $(t - T)$, is formulated as [8, 9]

$$-\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \tilde{m}_1}{\partial t}(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) + \mathcal{L}^\dagger \tilde{m}_1(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) = \mathcal{H}(t)\mathcal{H}(T - t)\Sigma_d(\mathbf{x}, E), \quad (13)$$

where \tilde{m}_1 is the solution of the first moment across phase space and time, Σ_d is the detector response function, and $\mathcal{H}(t)$ denotes the Heaviside step-function. Note that the adjoint flux has a domain only from the initial time to T. The equation for the second moment is formulated as [8, 9]

$$-\frac{1}{v} \frac{\partial \tilde{m}_2}{\partial t}(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) + \mathcal{L}^\dagger \tilde{m}_2(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) = \overline{v(v-1)\Sigma_f}(\mathbf{x}, E) \left(\int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \chi_p(E') \tilde{m}_1(\mathbf{x}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}', t) \right)^2, \quad (14)$$

where $\overline{v(v-1)}$ is the second factorial moment of induced fission, Σ_f is the fission cross section, and $(\int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \chi_p(E') \tilde{m}_1(E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}'))^2$ is the squared fission spectrum weighted adjoint flux for the first moment. It is important to note that the dependence of the higher order moments on the lower order moments adds inhomogeneity and non-linearity in the source term for order $n > 1$. Equations 13-14 need to satisfy the following terminal and boundary conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t_f) &= 0, \quad \mathbf{x} \in V, \boldsymbol{\Omega} \in 4\pi, E \in [0, \infty], \\ \psi^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t) &= \psi_b^\dagger(\mathbf{x}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}, t), \quad \mathbf{x} \in \partial V, \boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \mathbf{n} > 0, E \in [0, \infty]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

4. ANALYTICAL SOLUTIONS

It is important to verify the solutions from the novel Monte Carlo method by the use of analytical benchmarks. Beginning with the first moment of the count distribution from Equation 13, the assumption needs to be made that the medium is infinite, mono-energetic, and homogeneous. These assumptions lead to these generic formulations:

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{\bar{\nu}} \frac{dm_1}{dt}(t) + \Sigma_t m_1(t) &= \Sigma_s m_1(t) + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f m_1(t) + \mathcal{H}(t) \mathcal{H}(t_f - t) \Sigma_d, \\ -\frac{1}{\bar{\nu}} \frac{dm_2}{dt}(t) + \Sigma_t m_2(t) &= \Sigma_s m_2(t) + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f m_2(t) + \overline{\nu(\nu - 1)} \Sigma_f m_1^2(t). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

If these two equations need to satisfy the terminal condition in Equation 15, then the analytical solutions are obtained trivially by use of integrating factors as

$$\phi_1^*(t) = m_1(t) = \frac{\Sigma_d}{\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t} \left(e^{\nu(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)(t_f - t)} - 1 \right) \quad (17)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_2^*(t) = m_2(t) &= \\ &= \frac{\Sigma_d^2 \bar{\nu} (\nu - 1) \Sigma_f e^{2\nu(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)(t_f - t)}}{(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)^3} + \frac{2t\nu \Sigma_d^2 \bar{\nu} (\nu - 1) \Sigma_f e^{\nu(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)(t_f - t)}}{(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)^2} \\ &- \frac{\Sigma_d^2 \bar{\nu} (\nu - 1) \Sigma_f}{(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)^3} + \left(-\frac{\Sigma_d^2 \bar{\nu} (\nu - 1) \Sigma_f}{(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)^3} - \frac{2t_f \nu \Sigma_d^2 \bar{\nu} (\nu - 1) \Sigma_f}{(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)^2} + \frac{\Sigma_d^2 \bar{\nu} (\nu - 1) \Sigma_f}{(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)^3} \right) \times \\ &\quad \times e^{\nu(\Sigma_s + \bar{\nu} \Sigma_f - \Sigma_t)(t_f - t)}. \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

5. TEST PROBLEM PARAMETERS

A test case is considered to demonstrate the efficacy of the approach described in this work. The parameters for this test case were considered semi-arbitrarily, but some consideration is made to make it semi-analogous to existing experimental configurations. That is, the beryllium-reflected plutonium (BeRP) ball is used as a test case as it has been used for numerous neutron noise measurements. The BeRP ball has a measured mass of ~ 4.5 kg with a measured density of $\rho \sim 19.6$ g/cm³ [10]. The composition of the described system is illustrated in Table I.

With these material specifications, an MCNP6.3¹ simulation is conducted where the sphere is surrounded by a 10,000 cm radius sphere of isotopic ³He with an imposition of an albedo boundary condition with the reflectivity coefficient being 1. An F4 volumetric flux tally bounded all of the cells where an E4 card is used to specify an energy bin, $E_g = [0, 100]$ MeV. A multi-group cross section special tally treatment [11] is used in order to conduct a 1-group cross section collapse for applications involving the forward-adjoint code as well as the analytical solutions. The generalized “homogenized” macroscopic cross sections obtained from the 1-group collapse are shown in Table II.

The pdf for the number of prompt fission neutrons being emitted during a fission reaction, ν , for ²³⁹Pu is taken to be $P(\nu) : \{0.0071, 0.0674, 0.2283, 0.3263, 0.251, 0.0958, 0.0208, 0.0029, 0.0004\}$ [6], where $\bar{\nu} =$

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Table I. Isotopic compositions of the BeRP ball [6]

Isotope	Mass Fraction
^{238}Pu	1.493×10^{-4}
^{239}Pu	9.319×10^{-1}
^{240}Pu	5.899×10^{-2}
^{241}Pu	4.614×10^{-4}
^{242}Pu	2.787×10^{-4}
^{241}Am	2.656×10^{-3}

Table II. 1-group cross sections obtained from MCNP6

Cross Section	1/cm
Σ_t	3.407385×10^{-5}
Σ_f	8.73875×10^{-6}
Σ_c	2.53351×10^{-5}
Σ_s	0

3.1342 and $\overline{\nu(\nu - 1)} = 8.1106$. Furthermore, neutrons are assumed to be traveling at a constant speed of 10,000 cm/s where scattering reactions are not accounted for in order to achieve rapid asymptotic convergence by the forward-adjoint Monte Carlo.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The first moment solutions between the forward-adjoint Monte Carlo method and the analytical solution are compared in Figure 1. It is evident that the solutions align well, indicating that the forward-adjoint solution is accurately computing the first moment. Some discrepancies are observed when evaluating the residuals between the two plots, especially at the later times ($t > \sim 175 \mu\text{s}$). For the first moment, the residual maximum is observed to be ~ 0.25 . This discrepancy is potentially due to the fact that the terminal condition of $\phi^+(t = 200 \mu\text{s})$ is handled implicitly by the Monte Carlo implementation. Essentially, this discrepancy is related to the limitation of using a time-binning technique for obtaining a time-dependent adjoint flux.

The solution comparison of the second moments shown in Figure 2 behaves quite similarly to the first moment. The characteristic overestimation at the later times is still apparent for much the same reason as before, having a residual maximum at ~ 2.5 ; however, the Monte Carlo solution appears to have more noise at the earlier times. This is due to the fact that noise from the first forward-adjoint Monte Carlo solution is propagated into the second moment solution via its non-linear inhomogeneous source term.

Figure 1. Comparison of the first moments of the count distribution between the forward-adjoint Monte Carlo approach and the closed form analytical solution where the measurement period (gate-width) is 200 μs .

Figure 2. Comparison of the second moments of the count distribution between the forward-adjoint Monte Carlo approach and the closed form analytical solution where the measurement period (gate-width) is 200 μs .

7. CONCLUSIONS

The application of the forward-adjoint Monte Carlo methodology was successfully demonstrated for an infinite homogeneous test problem with material characteristics analogous to those of the BeRP ball. The preliminary results obtained from the forward-adjoint method agree well with the expectations given by the analytical solutions. The noise that is present, especially at later times, comes as a result of the discrete nature of the time-binning process in Monte Carlo simulations not allowing for an explicit terminal condition to be respected. The order of magnitude difference between the first and second moment residuals is a direct result of a combination of using a flux collision estimation as opposed to a path length estimation and noise from the previous solution being propagated through the adjoint source term for the second moment. Future work will include a comparison of the scoping calculations

with established neutron noise analysis in the forms of Feynman-Y calculations from list-mode data as well as investigation into the error propagation from one moment to the next. Implementation of the described method in a production level Monte Carlo transport code is also planned. This advancement will enable the Monte Carlo method to compute the full phase-space dependent solution of the neutron count distribution moments.

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